

Personal Data Management

Principles and Requirements for Processing Personal Data

In data protection law, “processing” means any operation which is performed on personal data, whether automated or not. This includes all actions with data, regardless of technology, medium (e.g. paper, digital, ...), or duration (temporary or permanent). Examples of data processing include collecting, storing, preserving, using, modifying, disclosing (e.g. granting access, forwarding or publishing), archiving, and destroying data.

Research involving personal data at a public institution, such as a university, is possible if certain conditions are met and the necessary precautions are taken. The following is a summary of the principles and requirements for processing personal data at the University of Basel:

Main principles of data protection

- **Rule of Law:** The processing of personal data must be based on a legal basis. The University statutes (§ 1) assign the University of Basel the responsibility of conducting research, which includes processing personal data.
- **Purpose limitation:** Data processing must always be carried out for a specific, stated purpose.
- **Proportionality:** Data processing must be necessary for the intended purpose and proportionate to the impact on privacy.
- **Accuracy (integrity):** Those who process personal data must ensure its accuracy.
- **Perceptibility of data processing:** Data subjects must be aware that their personal data are collected and processed.
- **Transparency:** Data subjects must be adequately informed about data processing, including which activities are being performed and their purpose. They also have the right to request information about their data at any time, without justifications.
- **Data security:** The data processing must comply with both technical and organizational security requirements.

Informed Consent

Informed consent from the data subject is required for specific processing related to an individual, which is typically the case in research.

The declaration of consent must...:

- specify the type and scope of the data and data processing
- include a reference to the intended use
- mention any possible disclosure of data to third parties
- list the data subject's rights (e.g. right of access, right to restriction of data processing, right to rectification, blocking or deletion of data)
- be voluntary; with no disadvantages for the data subject in case of refusing consent.

More information, fact sheets and templates:

can be found on the [website of the University's Data Protection Officer](#).

